

accelerate futureHEI

supporting future focused higher education

D5.1 Capacity Building Program: *Overview and Delivery Plan*

24.12.2023

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List of abbreviations

HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
ITAP	Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package
CEU	Continuing Education Unit
UBC	University-Business Collaboration
ESD	Education For Sustainable Development

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Project Consortium

University Industry Innovation Network BV (UIIN) - Netherlands

TUM International GMBH (TUMInt) - Germany

Momentum Marketing Services Limited (MMS) - Ireland

Instituto Superior Tecnico (IST) - Portugal

Universite De La Reunion (UR) – La Reunion, France

Canarias Universidad Europea De Canarias SL (UEC) – Canary Islands, Spain

Universidade da Madeira (UMa) – Madeira, Portugal

Fachhochschule St. Polten GMBH (STPUAS) - Austria

UC Leuven (UCLL) - Belgium

Magyar Agrar- Es Elettudományi Egyetem (MATE) - Hungary

Universitatea Politehnica Timisoara (UPT) - Romania

Vidzemes Augstskola (ViA) - Latvia

In the project, the university partners are represented by or focus the project work on unique departments across their institutions. Specifically:

- UEC: School of Architecture
- UMa: *Higher School of Technology and Management*.
- STPUAS: team of Service Unit Research and Knowledge Transfer
- UCLL: Business Management and Research & Expertise
- MATE: Institute of Agricultural and Food Economics
- ViA: management team and Faculty of Society and Sciences
- IST: Department of Civil Engineering, Architecture & Environment
- UR: ESIRI engineering school
- UPT: Digital Transformation Institute - ID/IFR and e-Learning Centre

Executive Summary: Capacity Building Program

What is this project about?

Led by [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), the **Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Accelerator Program** (Accelerate Future HEI project) will develop and test acceleration services to equip universities with the skills and capacity to drive their institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative. The project will apply a comprehensive methodology that builds on the status quo and develops a connected vision and set of activities that provide each institution with a tailored transformation action plan (ITAPs).

How does this project support universities?

What is this deliverable about?

This document presents an overview of the Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program that will be delivered across the duration of the project and which addresses the question *“How to best support the testing partners, based on their skills needs and challenges that they will address during the testing and implementation of the ITAPs?”*

The program is dedicated to professional development, peer learning and knowledge exchange in the areas relevant for institutional transformation towards an Entrepreneurial & Innovative University. The areas have been identified and validated through WP2 Current State Analysis and the Roadmap Workshops undertaken in WP3.

The overall learning framework includes the creation of learning experiences in the form of the Accelerate Training program as well as peer-learning and networking focused Cohort Knowledge Exchange events bringing all testing partners together.

This document further provides an overview of the target groups, training domains and approach, as well as the certification model and delivery plan.

01

Project Overview, Aim & Approach

An overview of the project's overarching goals, objectives, methodology and consortium.

Project Overview

The **Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Accelerator Program** (Accelerate_FutureHEI; thereafter referred as Accelerate Future HEI) project, under the coordination of [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), launched in January 2023 and is funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe program.

Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services for institutional transformation.

Main Aim

Accelerate Future HEI aims to **develop and test acceleration services to equip Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with the skills and capacity to drive their institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative.** To do that Accelerate Future HEI will apply a robust, comprehensive methodology that builds on the status quo and develops a connected vision and set of activities that provide each institution with tailored institutional transformation acceleration projects (ITAPs). Participating in this initiative provides the HEIs with a unique opportunity to identify key challenges they are facing and dedicate time and resources to develop solutions through unique ITAPs.

Through this project, the HEIs are not doing this alone, but instead receive personalised and peer-to-peer guidance through access to coaches, thematic working group workshops, training workshops and cohort knowledge exchange events. This allows HEIs to take a close internal look at what they want to achieve while receiving external support and guidance to enable them to implement these changes.

Key Objectives

IDENTIFY

the status quo of each HEI and its ecosystem regarding entrepreneurial and innovative activities.

DEVELOP

test and implement acceleration services that help institutions undertake a transformation roadmap and projects

BUILD

the capacity of the participating HEIs' staff to implement the transformation roadmaps through **a skills development program.**

EVALUATE

the strategies from HEIs supervised by an 'Acceleration Board' of **independent experts.**

GENERATE

policy feedback to the European Commission as well as provide widespread dissemination of the pilot results to other target groups.

Project Consortium

Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services.

Led by University Industry Innovation Network (UIIN), this ambitious project brings together twelve European partners from eleven countries to develop and implement acceleration services. The project consortium unites international experts on developing and supporting acceleration services, together with two established HEI consortia, one from the EIT HEI initiative (INCORE) and one from the European University Alliance (E³UDRES²) and EIT HEI Initiative (E.I.N.S). UIIN, together with TUM International and Momentum are referred to as *acceleration partners* to design and deliver the acceleration services and support the HEI *testing partners* as they implement their initiatives.

Our consortium represents institutions across Europe, including the Outermost Regions. The diversity of the partners will enable the development of overarching services that can be applied in different contexts and enable the HEIs to impact their regions.

Project Approach: Methodology

The project’s methodology is based on a **gap analysis** which involves a **three-phase approach** to understand the context, strategy, goals and status quo of each HEI testing partner and to provide an evidence-base and solid starting point to identifying areas and opportunities for institutional transformation. The research, development and implementation phases are underpinned and supported by training, evaluation, dissemination and other activities across the project duration.

Current State Analysis

WP2 | M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation.

Where are HEIs now?

The aim of this phase is to (1) clarify the desired future state and goals for institutional transformation and (2) understand the current state of each HEI testing partner and provide an evidence base for entrepreneurial and innovative activities at the partner universities. Specifically, WP2 involves activities of pre-scanning, asset mapping, focus groups, and survey. The survey findings will be explored in depth in this report.

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs

WP3 | M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

Subsequently this phase builds on the current state data to define and design an implementation plan to achieve the desired future state and institutional transformation goals and objectives, with regards to entrepreneurial and innovative activities including the identification of opportunities and challenges to address in acceleration services and coaching activities. This will be done through the roadmap workshops as well as Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs).

Acceleration services pilot-testing

WP4 | M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

This phase will support the testing partners in implementing the acceleration services and undertake actions towards institutional change, through a mixture of individual HEI and group-based support. Specifically, HEIs will undergo individual ITAP coaching with experts aligned to their core transformation focus areas, to then work on the implementation of their ITAPs and development of their investment strategy.

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program

WP5 | M1 – M48

HEIs will be supported with knowledge exchange and learning opportunities across the full duration of the project. In addition to the personalised coaching sessions, and the feedback, peer-to-peer feedback and mentoring guidance, which will be provided throughout *Phase 1* and *Phase 2*, HEIs will have access to dedicated events and workshops, including thematic Cohort Knowledge Exchange Events and Accelerate Training Workshops.

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation

WP6 | M1 – M48

The progress of the ITAPs will be tracked through a dedicated monitoring and evaluation mechanism to evaluate the impact and policy implications.

Communication and Dissemination

WP7 | M1 – M48

A communication and dissemination plan will be developed to share the transformation stories and the project’s key learnings to benefit the project’s community.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback

WP1 | M1 – M48

Adequate management and quality assurance processes and tools will be developed to deliver on the project’s outcomes and inform policy.

Project Approach:

Foundational conceptual model

The methodology within this project is based on a combination of research and practice. One of the key models underpinning the methodology is the **UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]** - the framework has been developed over 10 years of research and validated in practice to define the key elements of an entrepreneurial and innovative university, and the challenges and success factors associated with HEI transformation to become more entrepreneurial, innovative and engaged.

UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]

Main Deliverables

An overview of the main deliverables are outlined below, with the current delivered report highlighted.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback M1 – M48

The plan for how we will ensure we deliver on our outcomes & inform policy

D1.1
DMP M6

D1.2
Initial policy briefing M12

D1.3
Interim policy briefing M30

D1.4
Final policy recommendations report M48

Current State Analysis M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation. Where are HEIs now?

D2.1
Strategic Vision Statements – M12

D2.2
Synthesis Report – M12

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

D3.1
Roadmaps Analysis report - Draft M12

D3.2
Roadmaps Analysis report - Final M18

Acceleration services pilot-testing M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

D4.1
Summary report - common ITAP issues M12

D4.2
Case study report- ITAPs and results M48

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program M1 – M48

The plan for how HEIs gain skills and insights for acceleration & transformation

D5.1
Program overview & delivery plan M12

D5.2
Program delivery progress report & updated plan M30

D5.3
Summary of the learning outcomes M48

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation M1 – M48

We will monitor progress and evaluate impact of ITAPs

D6.1
Monitoring & evaluation plan – M12

D6.2
ITAPs Progress report – M30

D6.3
Final Impact Report

Communication and Dissemination M1 – M48

We plan to share our key learnings so others can benefit

D7.1
Initial Plan M6

D7.2
Updated plan & first dissemination report M12

D7.3
Interim dissemination report M30

D7.4
Final dissemination report M48

02

Accelerate Training Program

An overview of the process of defining and designing the six training domains, including their learning goals, target groups and learning modules.

Training program design

The Accelerate Training program aims to support the testing partners with their acceleration services, involving the HEI leaders, education and/or research focused academics and professional staff.

From challenges and needs to skills

Based on the Current State Analysis (WP2; read more in D2.2 Synthesis Report: Key findings on current state analysis) and the Roadmap Workshops, undertaken in WP3, **four key themes of challenges and opportunities** (read more in D3.1 Common challenges and solutions to becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative HEIs) for the institutional transformation towards a more engaged, entrepreneurial, and innovative university have been identified:

- **Entrepreneurial skills and mindset of students**, including fostering entrepreneurial skills and mindset among students going beyond traditional academic knowledge.
- **Impactful research and research valorisation** - envisioning and planning for research that goes beyond academic curiosity, in alignment with valorisation efforts to address real-world challenges.
- **Institutional support for engagement and innovation** through fostering support structures and institutional commitment, as well as capacity building for professional staff that facilitate support to entrepreneurial education and research
- **Partnership strategies for stronger engagement** through collaborative relationships and partnerships between university and regional and international external stakeholders in government, civic society and industry.

Defining training domains

Stemming from the above mentioned four themes, UIIN have identified **six training domains** to address the skill needs and challenges of different target groups across the nine testing partners. The training domains are classified as:

- Innovative education and entrepreneurial skills development
- Impactful research and research valorisation
- Holistic partnerships strategy & stronger external engagement
- Entrepreneurial development of the university
- Regional innovation hubs
- Engaged and entrepreneurial leadership

Defining target groups

The six training domains reflect the needs and challenges of three different stakeholder groups and therefore different training programs will target the different groups, specifically:

- **Professional staff** involved in business development, partnerships, university-industry engagement or entrepreneurship / valorisation
- **Leadership** involved in innovation, enterprise development, university-industry engagement, impact or entrepreneurship/ valorisation
- Education and/ or research focused **academics** interested in learning more about entrepreneurship, impact, industry engagement and valorisation (open to early, mid-career or senior academics, including PhD students)

In the next section a more detailed explanation about the six domains and examples of the potential courses that will be offered is provided.

Training Program Framework:

Six proposed training domains

Based on the identification of the nine testing partners' needs, six training domains are proposed for their academic, professional staff and leadership stakeholders. Within each training domain lay the envisioned learning objectives, the relevant target groups and a list of suggested courses.

1

Innovative education and entrepreneurial skills development

Tailored specifically for education-focused academics and faculty, this comprehensive training domain is designed to empower academics and educators with the tools and strategies needed to cultivate an entrepreneurial and innovative mindset among students. This training aspires to promote **educators' competencies**, so they not only are well-versed in **designing entrepreneurial curricula** and **utilising multidisciplinary education practices** but also capable of shaping the next generation of entrepreneurial leaders, through **supporting student entrepreneurship**, and integrating **sustainable development goals into education**.

2

Impactful research and research valorisation

The second training domain targets research-focused academics and faculty, and aims to equip them with the skills and knowledge necessary to extend the influence of their **research beyond traditional academic boundaries**, and explore **different research valorisation possibilities**. The key learning objectives further encompass **building compelling research communication skills** for research impact, along with skills to **integrate sustainable development goals into research** and encourage more interdisciplinary connections to enhance the impact and societal relevance of research endeavours.

3

Holistic partnerships strategy & stronger external engagement

The third domain proposes a training program focused on professional staff and leadership.

In an era marked by the interconnectedness of academic institutions and their broader ecosystems, this program is designed to equip participants with the **skills and strategies needed to cultivate meaningful partnerships and amplify external engagement**. The learning objectives include the establishment of collaborations between universities and their extended R&I ecosystem, while **maximising the impact** and **turning transactional relationships into transformative partnerships**. The program is specifically curated to support professional staff and leadership in **facilitating academics with building relationships with external stakeholders** and developing efficient processes for **mapping and evaluating collaborations**.

4

Entrepreneurial development of the university

In recognition of the transformative potential that entrepreneurialism holds for HEIs, the fourth training domain is crafted to empower professional staff with the **knowledge and tools necessary to foster an entrepreneurial culture within their universities**. The envisioned learning objectives revolve around **best practices for professional staff to help faculty build their entrepreneurial capacity, effectively valorise their research or initiate business ventures**. Moreover, the courses aim to delve into the development of **balanced and diverse career pathways** for academics, exploring the concept of an engaged university, and **embedding entrepreneurialism into the university's overarching strategy** and communication strategy.

5 Regional innovation hubs

The fifth training domain is carefully designed for professional staff and leadership that are interested in creating hubs and launch pads that serve as one-stop shops for entrepreneurship, acting as catalysts for seamless collaborations. The program will guide participants through the most important elements of establishing innovation hubs within the surrounding ecosystem. By participating in this training, professional staff and leadership will gain practical insights and tools to strategically position their institution at the forefront of regional innovation, while raising the awareness of their university's contribution to the development of the surrounding ecosystem.

6 Engaged and entrepreneurial leadership

The sixth training domain is designed exclusively for university leaders and senior management seeking to cultivate an environment of innovation and entrepreneurship within their institutions. This program is strategically curated to empower leaders with the proactive skills needed to foster an entrepreneurial culture and driving transformative initiatives. By participating in this training, leaders will gain insights and practical tools to create overarching sustainability strategies and effecting supporting structures that will steer their institutions towards a desired future marked by enduring innovative and entrepreneurial engagement.

Domain 1: Innovative education and entrepreneurial skills development

Key learning objectives

- Build and foster the entrepreneurial and innovative capacity and mindset of students
- Develop hands-on skills for students to start their own business
- Inspire, foster and preserve students' interest through external engagement
- Provide innovative education and apply innovative teaching methods
- Design and deliver the education curricula based on future needs of students

Target group:

Education-focused academics and faculty

1

Boundary Spanning Skills Education-driven UBC

This course will provide insights on engaging external partners in education design and delivery by learning from best practice examples across various university-business collaboration (UBC) types and explore how UBC in education aligns with and supports the institutional external engagement strategy.

2

Entrepreneurship at HEIs Teaching Entrepreneurship at Universities

A course to help participants in setting a vision for entrepreneurial education at university and explore innovative pedagogical approaches that can be apply for teaching entrepreneurship, including creating the right infrastructure and mobilising resources and personnel.

3

Entrepreneurship at HEIs Startup Success at Universities

This course will support establishing a vision for student entrepreneurship at university and learning about the support required for entrepreneurial teams and student start-ups. This includes practical tips for establishing successful university incubator or entrepreneurship centres.

4

Sustainability at Universities Education and sustainability

Participants will attain knowledge about how to integrate education for sustainable development (ESD) into university curricula across disciplines, exploring approaches and collaboration types to involve external stakeholders in developing relevant curricula and transferrable ESD competences.

5

Educators for Impact Instilling an innovative mindset

This course will focus on understanding the concept of an entrepreneurial and innovative mindset and its relevance to education, exploring and applying diverse tools and strategies to instill an entrepreneurial mindset and innovate teaching practices.

6

Educators for Impact Innovating learning journeys

In this course, participants will explore the benefits of using innovative and engaging pedagogies and educational tools, and learn diverse types of co-creation and co-delivery methodologies to enhance the content and delivery of the curriculum.

Domain 2: Impactful research and research valorisation

Key learning objectives

- Extend the impact of research beyond academia
- Understand the concepts of research and valorisation for sustainability and social innovation
- Generate cross-disciplinary research projects
- Conduct innovative and market driven research (through external engagement)
- Break down the silos between different academic programs and departments across education and research

Target group:

Research-focused academics and faculty

1

Impactful Researchers Impactful research

This course will provide an opportunity to explore how research conducted in academia can lead to both scientific and societal impact. It will address the process of planning for impact and different impact frameworks, discussing the importance of embracing an innovative mindset and engaging with external stakeholders.

2

Impactful Researchers External engagement and valorisation

The course will help testing partners enhance their external engagement by delving into UBC and its impact, exploring various knowledge transfer and valorisation pathways.

3

Impactful Researchers Communication and personal brand building

Participants will receive the knowledge and skills to build compelling research stories, effectively communicate research results and their impact to stakeholders, master the art of pitching initiatives, and explore strategies for creating a personal brand as an impactful academic.

4

Sustainability at Universities Research and valorisation for sustainability

In this course, testing partners will learn about integrating sustainability into research programs, fostering interdisciplinarity and collaboration to explore diverse pathways for addressing global and local sustainability challenges through research.

Domain 3: Holistic partnerships strategy & stronger external engagement

Key learning objectives

- Establish collaborations and partnerships across HEIs' R&I ecosystem
- Maximise impact through partnerships and stakeholder engagement for enhanced connectivity and synergies between the university and local public institutions or communities
- Support academics building bridges between university and industry
- Initiate, support and develop strategic partnerships with external stakeholders
- Develop and manage better processes in mapping and evaluating collaborations

Target groups:

Professional staff

Leadership

1

Boundary Spanning Skills Fundamentals of UBC

This course will provide fundamentals of UBC and relationship building across the various dimensions of the UBC Ecosystem Framework to better understand and support the process of fostering, promoting, and strengthening external relationships.

2

Boundary Spanning Skills UBC vision & culture

Participants will develop a strong foundation for success in external engagement by creating a vision for external collaboration. Additionally, they will gain insights on how to drive and nurture an innovative culture within their organisation.

3

Boundary Spanning Skills Impact of UBC

Participants will learn to better capture and articulate the achievements of UBC initiatives, using a comprehensive evaluation approach that combines quantitative and qualitative metrics alongside storytelling techniques to showcase success and exemplify best practices.

4

Building successful partnerships Navigating your partnership landscape

This course will focus on building a strong foundation for university-industry partnerships by first gaining a deep understanding of the internal and external ecosystem, including assets, structures, resources, and stakeholders.

5

Building successful partnerships Initiating & developing partnerships

This course introduces systematic approaches to define the desired and required qualities and characteristics of external partners, identify collaboration activities, and develop a personalised partnership approach that aligns with institution's objectives.

6

**Building successful
partnerships
From transactional to
strategic
partnerships**

In this course, participants will learn the characteristics and benefits of strategic partnerships as well as the different models and frameworks to facilitate the transition towards long-term, mutually beneficial partnerships.

7

**Building successful
partnerships
Maximising impact
through
partnerships**

This course will explore how to nurture, manage and measure partnerships through effective communication, relationship management, and evaluation strategies to proactively address challenges and maximise impact.

Domain 4: Entrepreneurial development of the university

Key learning objectives

- Build the entrepreneurial capacity of staff – improve knowledge, skills and experience of academics to valorise their research or start business
- Foster meaningful and applicable research and valorisation by academics
- Develop balanced and diverse career pathways for academics
- Understand the entrepreneurial and engaged university concepts and how they apply to their HEI
- Embed entrepreneurialism in university strategy
- Enhance visibility, awareness and communication of engagement and entrepreneurship internally and externally

Target groups:

Professional staff

1

Entrepreneurship at Universities
Enabling academic impact

In this course participants will explore different modes and activities of academic entrepreneurship and develop skills to encourage, promote, and provide tailored support for academics seeking to valorise their work beyond academia.

2

Entrepreneurship at Universities
Entrepreneurship impact at universities

This course will help understand the engaged university concept and explore ways to apply it for entrepreneurship development. This includes how to create, capture and communicate impact of entrepreneurship at universities.

3

Sustainability at Universities
Foundations of sustainability at universities

Participants will learn about the concept of sustainability at universities, identifying building blocks and key elements, defining concrete goals, and building a vision for a sustainable university.

Domain 5: Regional innovation hubs

Key learning objectives

- Create a hub or a launch pad for building entrepreneurship, as a one stop shop for external engagement
- Establish innovation hubs in the surrounding ecosystem
- Proactively initiate innovation projects in the region
- Enhance visibility, awareness and communication of engagement and entrepreneurship internally and externally

Target groups:

Professional staff

Leadership

1

Sustainability at Universities
Capturing impact of sustainable university

Participants will learn to create monitoring systems to assess the university's advancement towards sustainability objectives in education, research, operations, and governance. They will also explore various methods to clearly convey the impact of sustainability efforts.

2

Entrepreneurship at Universities
Nurturing entrepreneurial ecosystems

Participants will learn how to improve connections with local innovation and entrepreneurial networks. They will gather knowledge on building and organising knowledge-intensive areas and understand how to offer effective support for regional entrepreneurship.

3

Sustainability at Universities
Sustainability and community engagement

Participants will explore designing dedicated initiatives and programs to empower students and academics for sustainable development, creating support mechanisms and drivers for regional engagement to make an impact through effective partnering and collaboration.

Domain 6: Engaged and entrepreneurial leadership

Key learning objectives

- Be proactive and engaged leaders who nurture entrepreneurial culture through strategic changes
- Create long lasting, diverse funding models
- Provide sustainable governance and co-creation of infrastructures that last beyond leadership term

Target groups:

Leadership

1

Sustainability at Universities
Sustainable governance and operations

Participants will gain a deeper understanding of leadership aspects in a sustainable university, and learn how to create an overarching sustainability strategy, establish and manage supporting structures, operations, and facilities, reduce the university footprint, and embed a sustainability culture.

2

Entrepreneurship at Universities
Building entrepreneurship at universities

Participants will learn what it takes to be an entrepreneurial leader at a university and develop a comprehensive understanding of factors leading to success of entrepreneurship at universities. They will explore diverse real-world examples highlighting practical steps towards building entrepreneurship at universities.

03

Training approach

An overview of the proposed learning approach that will be used to deliver the Accelerate Training Program.

Training Approach

Drawing on the Current State Analysis (WP2) and key challenges identified in WP3, UIIN will design and deliver a range of courses to equip academics, professional staff and leaders within the testing partner HEIs with the skills needed to implement their ITAPs and drive change within their institutions.

As each HEI is different, it is important that the training approach is adaptable and flexible to the different needs. The training approach developed by UIIN has two unique aspects: (1) **flexible and diverse learning formats** to cater for multiple learning styles and (2) **a modular delivery framework**, to allow for customisable learning journeys.

Learning formats

To allow for interactivity, international and inter-institutional networking as well as effective learning, a flexible online learning format will be applied throughout the training. The delivery, timeframe and frequency of sessions will be tailored to meet testing partners' availability and commitments throughout the next 3 years of the project.

Participants will be equipped with the tools, resources and knowledge to enhance their understanding, analyse their own activities and develop concrete next steps for implementing their learnings in their daily work, all contributing to the strategic vision set previously in the project (WP2; read more in D2.1 Strategic Vision Statements towards becoming Entrepreneurial and Innovative Universities) and the ITAPs that will be developed in WP3 and implemented in WP4.

To cater for different **learning styles, schedules and expertise levels**, the program will be delivered in a flexible learning format. The training program features include:

- **Diverse session formats:** We use a variety of delivery formats (explained on the next page) to foster an ideal environment for comprehending theoretical concepts, good practice examples and implementing real-life skills.
- **Live and self-paced:** Workshops and knowledge to practice sessions require live participation, encouraging active collaboration and peer learning. Assignments and seminars offer the flexibility to be completed at your own pace.
- **Globally sourced materials:** Participants will have access an array of materials such as articles, blog posts, podcasts and instructional videos to supplement their learnings. These resources provide opportunities for in-depth exploration of topics covered during the course.

All the sessions will be delivered online via Zoom. The learning materials, assignments and peer reviews will be accessible via a personal learning environment managed by UIIN.

Modular approach

The training offerings will be structured in courses, using a **modular approach**. Courses can be grouped in thematical tracks as part of a larger training program, aligned to the six identified domains, or taken individually as stand-alone courses. The modular approach is the chosen vehicle for the learning delivery because it allows for customisable learning journeys, enabling participants to choose the courses that best supplement their skill needs, as well as provide concise and easily digestible knowledge.

A **course is a self-contained unit** that covers a specific topic using a **mix of learning modalities**. The learning modalities that we envision to use as part of the proposed courses include the following:

Interactive workshops

A mix of theory and facilitated discussions as well as hands-on activities allowing participants to co-create with peers.

Knowledge-to-practice sessions

Collaborative sessions under expert guidance, applying the gained knowledge to practice.

Fireside chats

Informal interviews with field experts sharing their unique perspectives.

Seminars

Focused, one-hour learning sessions delivered by experienced practitioners.

Individual and peer-reviewed reflections

Short assignments to contribute and receive valuable feedback from others.

Course assignments

Self-paced, peer-reviewed assignments to test the acquired knowledge and apply the new skills in real-life scenarios.

Self-paced resources

Course material and supporting resources like articles, case studies, podcasts and videos to supplement learning.

An **example course** could include, for instance:

- 1 or 2 guided interactive workshops of 2 hours combining a mix of theory, case studies, discussions and interactive short exercises;
- 1 or 2 Seminars of 1 hour delivered by an invited expert in the relevant topics, containing concrete insights or recommendations on the topic; AND / OR
- 1 or 2 Fireside Chats with invited experts in the field; AND / OR
- 1 practical session of 1-1.5 hours that provides participants a structured and interactive format to apply their gained knowledge on a practical group assignment.

As the testing partners develop their ITAPs, the training domains and course structures will be finalised to enable the testing partners to begin the training.

04

Cohort knowledge exchange events

An overview of the approach for peer learning & networking across the consortium and beyond.

Cohort Knowledge Exchange Events

In addition to the Accelerate Training Program, WP5 includes **Cohort Knowledge Exchange Events**, designed to bring the testing partners together to **create a shared knowledge base**, exchange findings and learnings and create a virtual meeting place for the HEIs to connect with peers, and other ecosystem actors, including investors and public funders.

The Cohort Knowledge Exchanges events are **held every 6 months**, providing testing partners with the opportunity to collaborate and connect with one another. Testing partners will be able to **openly share** their findings, learnings, and best practices, while also gaining valuable insights from their peers. Additionally, these events will serve as a **meeting place** where testing partners can connect with various ecosystem actors, such as investors and public funders. This will **facilitate meaningful discussions**, networking opportunities, and potential collaborations that can further enhance the impact and success of the cohort's initiatives.

Each event will have a **dedicated theme** which is chosen relevant to the specific phase of the project implementation and the corresponding needs of the testing partners. For example, the first event, delivered in Month 6, was organised to support the testing partners developing their Strategic Vision Statements (part of WP2 Current State Analysis).

Following this approach, the theme of upcoming Cohort Knowledge exchange events will be matched to the most relevant activities or challenges that are happening at the project: for example, defining the Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs), building an investment strategy, expanding external partnerships, addressing specific skills gaps etc.

Every second Cohort Knowledge Exchange Event will take place on site, adjacent to a partner meeting, which will provide an opportunity for site visits or more hands on learning

opportunities.

Furthermore, the annual UIIN conference, which brings over 500 individuals from around the world working on university-industry engagement, research valorisation and entrepreneurial and innovative universities, will be considered as a potential platform for the knowledge exchange event. Integrating the project into this community of practice would promote the learnings of the project to the wider university-industry engagement community and enable the testing partners to exchange insights with a global expert community.

Insights from Knowledge Exchange Event 1 (M6)

- The **first event** was dedicated to support testing partners in defining the **Strategic Vision Statements (SVS)**; as part of WP2).
- During the first part of the event , partners were presented with **background information** about the purpose of SVS for HEIs and an **overview of good practice examples**.
- In the second part of the event, testing partners **engaged in an interactive workshop** facilitated by the UIIN team.
- Participants were guided through a series of **interactive exercises** in an online collaborative tool “Mural” in order to draft preliminary SVS based on their specific institutional context and focus.
- Testing partners had a chance to **exchange their insights and experience**, and find common challenges and solutions for approaching the task.
- The event concluded with a **plenary session** where participants shared insights, lessons learned, and actionable takeaways.

05

Certification model & delivery plan

Certification model & delivery plan

To address the diverse skills gaps across the testing partners, UIIN will heavily rely on the evidence from the WP2 investigation (more information about it can be found in D2.2 Synthesis Report: Key findings on current state analysis) and the needs identified during the WP3 Roadmap Workshops (more information about this process can be found in D3.1 Common challenges and solutions to becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative HEIs) to design and deliver a full portfolio of different courses across the identified thematic domains in the next 3 years of the project lifecycle.

UIIN will utilise the framework of Continuing Professional Development that uses the Continuing Education Units (CEUs) system to acknowledge the learning and skills acquired from the courses and workshops. One CEU is awarded for eight hours of active learning.

Upon successfully completing a course within the Accelerate Training Program, the participants will earn a UIIN micro-credential in a form of a shareable digital badge. They will also receive 1.5 CEUs that can be used to receiving a professional certification.

How will this work for the testing partners?

UIIN will be develop and share a regular training calendar (at least every quarter) outlining the upcoming courses from the portfolio of different offerings catering to the three target groups (academics, professional staff, leadership) and addressing the needs under the identified domains:

- Innovative education and entrepreneurial skills development
- Impactful research and research valorisation
- Holistic partnerships strategy & stronger external engagement
- Entrepreneurial development of the university

- Regional innovation hubs
- Engaged and entrepreneurial leadership

Furthermore, any new relevant domains that might emerge in the process of ITAP implementation, as well as following the developments in the Higher Education landscape might be included in the updated Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange program.

The testing partners will be asked to disseminate the training information internally to invite relevant colleagues to choose from the different training options and sign up for the courses that are most suitable to them.

To meet the KPIs of the Accelerate Future HEI project, and ensure widespread learning that can be implemented across the institution, each testing partner will need to ensure:

- Minimum 3 participants trained per target group
- Minimum 4 courses completed per target group

The training approach outlined in this report, including the six training domains, learning formats and modular framework will provide the testing partners with flexibility to adapt their training in line with their SVS and ITAPs, and enable various colleagues within the institutions to enhance their capabilities and skills in entrepreneurial and innovative development.

Follow our journey

To learn more visit the project www.acceleratefuturehei.eu

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